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THE IMPORTANCE OF THE CHILD'S CONTACT WITH THE NATURE THESE DAYS

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THE PENCIL

Manoel de Barros

The nature of God is too great.
I wanted to make myself a little nature particular.
So small that it could fit on the tip of my pencil.
If it were her, I wish, just the size of my backyard.
just one tamarin tree was going to grow for use by birds.
And let the mornings prepare other birds to compose the blue of the sky.
And if it wasn't too much to ask, I would like at the bottom flowed a river.
The most important thing
What I wanted was the river.
In the river, me and our group, I would all go day to play cangapé in running waters.
That, I think, would be my little nature particular:
As far as my little pencil could reach.

INTRODUCTION

The future has arrived and with it many questions that not even the most fertile imagination would have been able to imagine a few years ago. The world has changed, and that includes entertainment, routine, machines... life! Today, technology undoubtedly allows us to do a lot of interesting things. We can maintain daily contact with distant relatives, meet old friends, and go shopping without leaving home, among thousands of other wonders. But how to evolve without creating a distance from the benefits of the primitive?

“Gathering the clay from our humus to remake humanity in us by hand. “
(Piorsky)

Today we live in a culture that values the sense of sight too much, to the point of ignoring others. We don't have time to stop to smell the smells of life, we don't pay attention to small sounds and even less let our skin feel different textures that are everywhere. But what do we see if we no longer allow ourselves to even observe the moments where memories are created naturally because we want to photograph everything at all times?

Our children, from a very young age, are already spectators of ready-made elements. They do not need to create and are not challenged to travel with their ideas, as they are born being bombarded by a series of technological contents. An excess of colors, music, and, mainly, commercial appeal.

Thus, more and more, the little ones are breaking the cycles of relationships and many have come to think that food comes from the market, that milk comes from the carton, and that certain animals, such as sheep, do not even exist in real life. We are increasingly creating consumers and not citizens! We deal with a generation that finds it difficult to have fun and that always needs to bring something along to entertain itself, which can be an electronic device or even anti-stress toys. Very young people, but who from an early age already carry health problems, such as obesity, anxiety, and insomnia. They are children raised indoors, often small, and who, even when they have the chance to be outdoors, are in cars or strollers.

“Science can classify and name the organs of a

thrush,

but cannot measure its charms.

Science cannot calculate how many horses' strength exists in the song of a thrush. Anyone who accumulates too much information loses the ability to guess: divine The thrushes divine.”
(Manoel de Barros)

The problem is real and far more serious than most want to accept. The sooner the change begins, the better for everyone. But where to start? Perhaps the simplest answer is all around us, in our history and our ancestral memories. What the modern, scientific, and commercial world may only consider “child's play”, “playing in the dirt” or even “mess”, maybe the key for us to return to having more active, healthy children and nourishing their imaginations.

“Contact with nature improves all the most important milestones of a healthy childhood – immunity, memory, sleep, learning capacity, sociability, physical capacity – and has significantly contributed to the overall well-being of children and young people. The evidence points out that the benefits are mutual: just as children and adolescents need nature, nature needs children and young people.” (Children and Nature Program and Brazilian Society of Pediatrics, 2019)”

There is still a long way to go for nature to regain the place it has lost in the lives of young people over generations, but some families, schools, and professionals are taking their role seriously and it is already possible to see the results. The following work aims to show how important nature is to people's lives in general, but especially to children. Aiming to relate information from a vast bibliography, courses, and the daily observation of children from two classes of 1st year of Elementary School, within the Escola Vira-Virou, in Rio de Janeiro, where children are encouraged to explore and interact with the environment daily. The observations and interviews were carried out in a wide space, with a dirt floor, some fruit trees, and a small tree house made entirely of wood. This school space is called “Orchard” and even though it is just one of the places for free activities and games that the school has, it is, by far, the preferred one by the vast majority of children.

HOW CAN CONTACT WITH NATURE BENEFIT CHILDREN?

According to Vygotsky (1989), we consider that children constitute themselves in culture and are producers of culture. However, we understand that humans are, simultaneously, beings of culture and beings of nature. Its development takes place in the interaction with members of a species that has historical, cultural, rational, linguistic, and political specificity (LOUREIRO, 2006; GUIMARÃES, 2006). Thus, children are beings who are constituted in connection with other beings, human and non-human and are empowered in this state of connection (ESPINOSA, 1983).

According to Chauí (2001, pg. 209), “nature is the active principle that animates and moves beings, a spontaneous force capable of generating and caring for all beings created and moved by it. (...) the substance of beings. It throbs within every human being as an intimate feeling of life”. It is the substance present in all things and beings that make up the cosmos. From this perspective, human beings are part of nature. As in the philosophy of the pre-Socratics (Bornheim, 2001), Nature is life itself, in its physical-affective manifestations. We go through many changes, but biologically we are the same creatures.

Thus, all the vain effort that human beings make to distance themselves from their origins, innate affinities, or being superior to nature, is initially ignored by children. They appreciate the land, the water, and especially the mixture of these: the mud! They show an intimacy with these elements, which we have already lost, due to lack of habit, time, or having been pruned when we were younger. Even though it has not yet been scientifically used,

the term “Nature Deficit Disorder” created by LOUV (2008) has a clear and frightening concept of what the absence of contact with nature can bring negatively to human life, especially during childhood, such as decreased use of the senses, difficulty concentrating, and higher rates of physical and emotional illness.

By playing with what the earth gives us, the child is creating a bond with nature, its roots, and its ancestors. The toy made by her with natural materials allows her ability to create to be discovered and explored. Gradually, he remodels the world with everything he imagines. Children’s imagination needs to be nurtured to expand and when there are no stimuli it is atrophied. For Bachelard (1991), “the imagination is a fourth kingdom of nature, where the universe of inhabiting, fitting in and resignifying exists”.

Vygotsky (1998) also highlights the role of the act of playing in the construction of children’s thinking, as it is by playing that child reveal their cognitive, visual, auditory, tactile, and motor states, their way of learning and entering into a cognitive relationship. with the world of events, people, things and symbols.

“The materiality of playing, when it consists of unscientific material substances, decomposed, dismantled by time or coming from nature, has the power to unframe the imagination. It allows the child to create with greater freedom his experience.”
(PIORSKY, 2016)

The hallmarks of a healthy childhood - immunity, memory, learning ability, sociability, and physical disposition - are supported by contact with the natural environment. Research by the Criança e Natureza Program, the Alana Institute, and the Brazilian Society of Pediatrics, also points out that these benefits are mutual because just as children need nature, nature needs them.

The interaction with natural materials also works to sharpen the senses and raise awareness of the child’s body. Through sounds, the child gets closer to the nature of things (wood, iron, glass...) and becomes more and more awake to perceive the details of the world. As for the smell, real odors (even the most fetid ones) help us discover the identity of things.

Free play is not encouraged as it is not profitable for anyone. Increasingly stringent restrictions, the excessive development of cities, condominium rules, and necessary environmental regulations are showing, without noticing, that free play is not a good option. But it is not news to many that outdoor activities or other types of contact with natural elements bring health benefits. In the 1970s, land activities were already used to treat the mentally ill and before that, in the 1950s, gardening began to be used as therapy. Currently, zootherapy has already had its effectiveness proven, with pets helping their owners to control high blood pressure. But unfortunately, the use of nature as an additional or preventive alternative therapy, especially with children, is still being ignored.

“Contact with nature influences the way children learn. Learning in a natural context allows direct experiences with the subject, making it more interesting and easier to understand.” (Moss 2012, Erikson and Ernest 2011).

It is a fact that the natural open environment is the main source of sensory stimulation that a child can have. It encourages fantasy, and make-believe and enables choices for creative engagement. The child can learn things long before they are subject in school. This is made clear in the following dialog: When observing the children in the “orchard”, a first-year student who is usually extremely agitated, has been reflecting for many minutes in front of a large puddle of mud. So he talks to the teacher who doesn't know if stepping into the puddle will cover his foot.

The teacher says:

- Is this puddle too deep?

And he, visibly intrigued, replies:

-I don't know how to measure!

The teacher trying to instigate him asks:

-How do you think we can measure things?

- I think I'll use my hand!

And so he did, placing his hand sideways in the center of the muddy water, which covered all his fingers. But still not satisfied:

-I don't know if the big puddle is all the same “size”.

- And what can we use to measure?

He was thoughtful because he did not imagine that he was allowed to put any measuring instrument in the water. So, the teacher suggested that the boy

take a ruler to measure the height of all the points in the puddle. At that moment his eyes shone with joy! And the person in charge even gave him a challenge to choose one of the two rulers, the big one or the little one, that was on his table. The boy, who has several socio-affective issues and is constantly in need of help to maintain control of his body and his actions, spent several minutes having fun in the orchard, getting to know different depths, testing his limits, and creating new hypotheses and knowledge. At that moment, he became the center of attention of a group that was previously engaged in another game but loved the idea of seeing him measuring the depth of the puddle.

“Reality is what is happening out there, not what is happening in your mind or on your computer screen.”

(Paul Dayton, Marine ecologist)

In the space of natural playing, leadership is often given by creativity or other criteria, which are not physical. This creates the opportunity for different children to exercise leadership and manage to show their ideas and personality, removing the focus that was often on who was the best at sports or the most resourceful or extroverted.

Naturalistic intelligence needs to be valued, developed and appreciated like others. Typical of those who have a strong connection with nature and an unusual ability to identify and distinguish animals, plants, climate formations, and other elements of the natural world. At school, they have more facilities in Biology and Geography.

Many see technology as the salvation of the world and believe that only through it will we be able to evolve or reach success. They do not see the harmful effects of screens, but they are afraid of nature and end up passing on excessive fears to their children. Of course, it's understandable that the sharp rise in violence is causing adults to rethink where they should take their children. However, research on the benefits of nature should also be taken into account at this time. According to Louv, studies suggest that exposure to nature reduces symptoms of ADHD, and improves resistance to stress, depression, and also cognitive skills.

Playing in an open environment children learn about the world, even about caring for and

preserving their environments. A place like this also stimulates more vibrant social and neighborhood relationships, as they can become spaces for living together, leisure, and games, providing fun moments in groups.

The elements of nature can help children develop a sense of self-regulation and risk management, which builds autonomy and responsibility. Adults can observe, but without intervening directly, so that they discover the real risks of their attitudes, challenge themselves and increase their self-esteem. A wide and natural space serves as an invitation to practice physical activity, helping to combat obesity and other problems very common in modern children.

But it is important to emphasize that for children any nature is enough! Backyard space makes no difference and often a backyard game becomes more interesting than a mountain expedition.

“I think the backyard where we played is bigger than the city. We only discover this after we grow up. We discover that the size of things has to be measured by the intimacy we have with things. It has to be like it happens with love. Thus, the pebbles in our backyard are always bigger than the other stones in the world. Precisely for the reason of intimacy (...)” (Manoel de Barros)

NATURE IN SCHOOLS

If experts are making an effort every day to show the benefits of growing up in contact with nature, the little ones love being outdoors so much, and today the school occupies a large space in the lives of children, what would be the responsibility of this institution and their educators, in distancing the little ones from the natural environment?

According to BNCC, the Natural Sciences area aims to promote scientific literacy, so that students understand and interpret the natural world and can transform it. To do so, they need to get in touch with nature and reconnect with it, through theory and practice, used as a pedagogical tool to work on different skills. By exploring nature and its different elements, in the most varied situations, the child is discovering and apprehending the world, essential since kindergarten.

But the reality is far from that. When visiting most schools, we still found cold environments, a lot of plastic, and an empty and lifeless spaces. These environments, despite all the evolution in the world, are stuck in the past. They are places where there is no time or space to live and be happy because the “priorities” are different. Concern for the future, anxiety, and lack of habit make parents (and consequently some children) think that playing is a waste of time.

Normally, those responsible believe that sports or Physical Education classes are equivalent to playing time, but this is not true! The idea is to have moments reserved for playing without structure and adult intervention so that the experience is valid and complete. Planned activities, even outdoors, are generally weaker in long-term memory than spontaneous experiences.

Unfortunately, it is still rare for people to see the potential and importance of life in childhood. For many years, children’s lives were not taken into account and their wishes and needs were never heard. Schooling was intended to indoctrinate ideologies and the accumulation of goods and information. The intention was only to reproduce what was being done and being different was not an option.

In the past, children were less aware of what happens to the planet, but they used the outdoor spaces much more for leisure activities. One explanation for this is that any kind of problem was not “children’s business” and it was not common for adults to spend their time trying to explain what was happening with nature or about many other subjects. Another is that people lived many decades alienated, believing and acting as if everything that nature gives us is eternal.

Contact with nature needs to be part of school activities so that children understand its importance and are engaged with environmental preservation. It is also the responsibility of schools to help young people become a generation that will find solutions to the crises that humanity faces today. It will be up to them to seek to control pollution, manage non-renewable resources, use energy better, conserve the soil, protect biological diversity, and reduce waste production, among many other problems that they will inherit.

For this, it is necessary to teach them sustainable practices in the use of natural resources, based on the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) proposed by the UN. The SDGs propose global actions so that by 2030 we have better living conditions on the planet, based on sustainability, according to the 15th objective: “Terrestrial Life”. “Protect, restore and promote the sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss”.

According to child and nature expert Chawla, “The positive effects of developing with nature on health, concentration, creative play and bonding with the natural world can form the basis for developing an environmental awareness.”

If children are not attached to nature and everything that is part of it, they will not reap the benefits of that contact and will not feel committed to taking care of it. It’s a cycle! It is necessary to have a link, a relationship of belonging so that they feel responsible for the care, from the most basic. The contact with nature allows the biopsychosocial development of the child, which establishes a healthy interaction between him and the environment in which he lives, which includes the environment as an integral part of the social, psychological, and biological aspects of the individual.

Still according to Chawla, if the child has the habit of playing freely in a natural space until the age of 11, he will probably become a person more concerned with the environment in the future. She also uses the term “contagious caring attitude”, referring to an adult who has a good attitude toward the environment and becomes a reference for children. The crisis in ecology is rooted in the way we educate future generations. Today, education often ends up alienating life to emphasize what will bring future success and financial return.

Walks, even if sporadic and to nearby places, connect students to the surroundings and initiate the “belonging process” to the space. Vegetable gardens, butterfly gardens, land spaces, and lawns are simple examples that can make the school space more attractive. A visionary school management or a conscientious teacher can be the catalyst for the beginning of an important process of change.

“All places are places to learn. Forests, backyards, and territories are to be investigated, with trees, rivers, clearings, squares, and beaches. nature is a wealth of possibilities for aesthetic education, not only for children, as for all human beings.” (BARBIERI, 2012, p.115).

During a conversation with a student who played in the “Pomar,” I asked:

- What do you like to do most here at school?

He, without hesitating for a second, replied:

- Play in the orchard!

Unsurprisingly, I wanted to find out more:

- But what do you like to do here?

- I like to play after the rain, when there’s mud and everything looks like poop. It’s cool to jump in and watch the mud rise!

Still wanting to challenge him, I asked:

-But when it’s dry you don’t like to come here, right? No puddles at all!

-I like it! I like to run around and play with the gemstones when it’s dry.

- What stones are those?

- The round ones I use to make necklaces or the ones that look like I caught them on the moon. – he replied, showing me some small seeds and some grains of earth.

-Do you like to do anything else here in the orchard?

-All! Once we even heard a story here!

Generally, children are confined for most of the school period, as if reality were reduced to the internal spaces of classrooms, and they were born for school, not for the world. According to Tibira (2006), there are two main reasons why children are imprisoned: “The ideology of the built space” and the “Culture of cleanliness” and both are very common in schools today. The first consists of occupying all spaces on the land with the construction of rooms, doing away with all the green areas and external spaces that could be used by children for various activities, and prioritizing closed spaces. The second and no less serious or important issue is what she called “Cleaning culture”, which talks about children not being able to get dirty, as they need to be handed over to those responsible exactly the way they arrived at school.

THERE IS STILL HOPE

“Currently, the greatest modernity is to return to essences.”

(Lea Tiriba, Environmental educator and teacher)

Humans are losing their ability to experience the world directly. Internet addiction is already a reality and some studies relate the highest rate of depression to those who access the network more. This panorama occurs due to the accelerated growth of Internet access and new technologies, naturally leading to a greater sedentary lifestyle and emotional seclusion.

“On the horizon of the set of reasons and questions presented about the situation of children being confined, one conclusion is that being outdoors is not a definition, a pedagogical imperative, but an option for each individual.

school, teachers or adults responsible for the children.”

(Tiriba, 2006)

What we often find in schools are tight and inadequate spaces. The most important thing for many is that they have chairs, tables, and a board to show the syllabus. It would be incredible if every school presented architecture that contemplated the body, sun, greenery, and trees, but this is far from reality. One possible option is to visit nearby places and use every possible space in the school: a small garden has great potential! And also bringing nature into the children’s daily lives in another way: offering earth, water, stones, seeds, and clay, preparing an environment with natural artifices. In this way, nature becomes not something distant. It comes into existence and this tactile experience, of smell, of color, materializes. This makes it much easier to start connecting with her.

“Among the schools in our network, one of the ones with the smallest patio is one of the ones with the greatest diversity of possibilities for children, with a variety of trees, a compost garden, and different areas for playing. Materializing a courtyard proposal is much more in the design than in the financial resource”

(Rita Moraes, Pedagogical Adviser for Early Childhood Education at the Novo Hamburgo Municipal Department of Education)

To improve future generations, it is necessary to have a broader vision and change, even if small, now so that the results come in the long term. The reality today is still that we rarely find bare feet, we see nature being used only as decoration, and contact with water is made only for hygiene. It is difficult to teach them to enjoy the good that nature does and to respect it without having contact with it. This role of presenting the natural environment to the child belongs to the family and can also be performed by the school.

According to Robin Moore, a university professor, children live by the senses whose experiences connect the outside world to the inside. The natural environment is the main source of sensory stimulation and the freedom to play and explore is essential for healthy development.

It was enchanting to observe the Pomar’s moments carefully for weeks and to observe the real power of nature. Understanding how agitated children can calm down using only earth, how introverted children manage to lead games, even for a few minutes, and realize the joy of the little ones every day when after lunch we said: “You can go to the orchard!” For many long minutes, I compared those moments with those I experienced in my childhood, in a good school with great natural potential, but which was never used! Would I have more running skills if my school looked like this? Would I be less afraid of bugs? Would I be less ashamed to expose myself in certain games? Doubts permeate the mind!

The observations make clear the child’s need for space and how this space makes their ideas flow. I saw tree leaves turn into dolls, children turn into

jaguars and walk on 4 “paws” and the land turns into food. I was able to observe the sale of stones and coffee made from muddy water by girls who, at the age of 6, say they have cell phones and dance apps. In this regard, it is worth mentioning that Piorsky talks about toys extracted from nature going beyond the issue of consumption, as there is something immaterial of unique importance in them. This was also clear when we made dolls using green mango and sticks. At that moment, I’m proud to have been the adult who made the difference, because they wanted dolls and didn’t know how to make them. I gave the idea of using the green mangoes that fell still small, as some tribes still do today, and quickly each child appeared proudly displaying their “son” made of fruit and sticks.

Therefore, I conclude that healing the lost bond is not impossible but quite necessary. To improve future generations it is necessary to have a broader vision and that changes are made now so that the results come in the long term. We can already see that in some places changes are starting to take shape, as they have already begun to realize that physical and mental health depends on the environment.

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